

Impact of Nutritional Status on Cognitive Development among Pre-School children of Varanasi

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Abstract

Malnourished children have been found to exhibit a wide range of cognitive abnormalities. It is a condition developed due to inadequate micronutrient intake in the diet. Poor intake of food causes long-term cognitive consequences that affect preschooler brain functions. Unhealthy dietary habits, low socio-economic conditions and lack of nutritional awareness increase malnutrition risk among children. The objective of the study was to determine the impact of nutritional status on cognitive development among 3-5 years pre-school children of Varanasi. A cross-sectional study was implemented among 200 participants, who were selected randomly from Anganwadi centers of Varanasi. The data were collected through Interview schedule that contains information regarding food habits, food intake, and anthropometric assessment. The Seguin Form Board Test used for testing children's cognitive development. Collected data was analyzed by SPSS. The outcomes of the study indicated that lack of nutritional knowledge among mothers and poor dietary habits negatively impact children's cognitive development status. The study found that most children were wasted, and less than fifty percent were stunted. There are needs to be proper nutritional awareness programme related to child nutrition.

Keywords: Malnutrition, Dietary Habits Pre-School Children, Cognitive Development, Nutrition

INTRODUCTION

The most important factor influencing brain growth is nutrition, which is also a component of the biological environment that can influence cognitive development. Stunted and wasted growth, reduced immune response learning and cognitive development abnormalities, and undernutrition are all experienced by children on low-protein, low-calorie diets. On the other hand, inadequate vitamin intake in school-age children has been associated with developmental delays, reduced immunity, improper behaviour, and growth retardation. Every single one of these things reduces a child's cognitive development (Nadeem & Fatima, 2007). Malnutrition is caused by a variety of etiological factors, unhealthy eating patterns, and a lack of consumption of fruits and vegetables. One of the challenges is not knowing what kinds of foods are appropriate for weaning. Numerous dietary factors can impact cognitive development, and an individual's consumption of specific micronutrients may have an interaction effect on the brain (Ansuya et al., 2023). The effects of undernutrition, most commonly protein-energy malnutrition, on children's cognitive development in developing nations have been studied by numerous researchers. Malnutrition affects the brain in a number of ways, including memory issues, intellectual slowness (particularly in reading, writing, and math), and other cognitive deficiencies (Kumari & Gupta, 2020). Micronutrients are just one of the many factors that affect brain growth and cognitive development. They have a substantial correlation with enhanced cognitive performance. The capacity to process information using perception, learning, memory, thinking, and attention is known as cognition (Hioui, 2019).

According to WHO estimates, 50 million children under five are overweight, 159 million are stunted, and 41 million are wasting (WHO, 2022). The majority of children on the planet experience severe acute

malnutrition. It is well established that there is a strong correlation between poor diet and cognitive deterioration (UNICEF,2022). Malnutrition-related cognitive deficiencies might manifest as memory problems, intellectual slowness, or specific learning difficulties in reading, writing, and numerical ability. The child's behavior could indicate the presence of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, emotional management problems, or socialization concerns (M. et al., 2016).Only 2.5% of children come into the extremely excellent I.Q. category, whereas the majority of children (64.2%) fall into the low category. This is according to recent study. Thus, children's cognitive development in both rural and urban areas is improper for our developing country(Tiwari, 2021).

The purpose of this research is to raise awareness among parents about diet management and its impact on cognitive functions, with the goal of reducing the rate of malnutrition among children worldwide. It also aims to enhance memory, attention, Intelligence, and academic achievement by shedding light on the role that nutritional diets and supplements play in cognitive development. In Anganwadi centers, a large number of preschoolers suffer from low cognitive abilities. The main objective of the study is to establish the correlation between malnutrition and cognitive development.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in the selected Anganwadi centers of Varanasi city, Uttar Pradesh. A cross-sectional study was carried out, and a simple random sampling technique was used. A total of 200 school-going children (3-5 years) were selected. The age group for the study was decided from Piaget's theory of cognitive development. Data were collected using an interview schedule, and the Seguin Form Board Test (SFBT) was used for the assessment of cognitive development(Basavarajappa, 2009). The interview schedule was used to collect general information, food consumption pattern, and anthropometric assessments. Five food group plans were used for the assessments of the food frequency as per the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) (Swaminathan, 2020). Assessments of height and weight were used to determine each child's nutritional status. The WHO's 50th percentile growth chart was used to compare the subjects' height and weight. The nutritional status of the pre-school children was assessed using the Waterlow classification standards(Arya, 2020).The standard stunting (height for age) and Wasting (weight for height) are estimated by the Waterlow Classification. The WHO 50th percentile growth chart was used as a reference for the child's standard height and weight based on age.Data were analyzed using the statistical software SPSS. The Chi-square test was used to test the significance of the association between nutritional status and cognitive status. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table - 1 Distribution of Pre-School children according to their age and gender

Age (in years)	Frequency	Boy	Girl	Percent
3	49	23	26	24.5
4	76	42	34	38
5	75	45	30	37.5
Total	200	110	90	100.0

Source: Authors calculation

Table -1 shows the distribution of respondents according to age. In the table, 24 percent of respondents were in age of 3 years,38 percent in the age of 4 years, 37.5 percent in the age of 5 years,Table no.1 also shows the distribution of respondents according to the age. The maximum no. of boys are 110 (55%) and girls are 90 (45%) in the age group 3-5 years.

Table -2 Nutritional status of Pre-School children according to Waterlow Classification

Category	Stunting		Wasting	
	N	Percent	N	Percent
Normal	154	77.0	34	17.0
Mild	16	8.0	36	18.0
Moderate	18	9.0	58	29.0
Severe	12	6.0	72	36.0
Total	200	100.0	200	100.0

Source: Authors Calculation

Table-2 shows that 77% of respondents had results that were standard for their age and height. Additionally, this table showed the proportions of respondents who had mild, moderate, and severe stunting, which were 8%, 9%, and 6% of the total. In addition, 17% of respondents were found to be normal based on their weight for age; the results and table indicate that mild wasting accounted for 18% of the samples, moderate wasting for 29%, and severe wasting for 36%. The Waterlow formula was used to determine the percentages of stunting and wasting. The WHO's norm for height and weight was used.

Table -3 Distribution of Pre-School children according to their food habits and cognitive development

Cognitive Development status	Very Superior	Superior	High Average	Average	Below Average	Borderline defective	Mild	Moderate	Total
Vegetarian	4	6	20	20	18	16	14	4	102
Non-Vegetarian	4	8	8	32	18	20	8	0	98
Total	8	14	28	52	36	36	22	4	200
$\chi^2 = 14.2$, df = 7, P<0.048									

Source: Authors Calculation

Table-3 indicates that eating a non-vegetarian diet had a greater impact on the development of mental ability than eating a vegetarian diet. Most of the respondent were from average cognitive development category (52 respondents) out of which 32 were consuming non-veg food and 20 were consuming veg food.

Table-4 Distribution of Pre-School children according to their nutritional status (height for age) and cognitive development

Cognitive Development status	Very Superior	Superior	High Average	Average	Below Average	Borderline defective	Mild	Moderate	Total
Normal	8	12	24	48	22	24	12	2	152
Mild	0	0	0	0	2	4	8	2	16
Moderate	0	0	4	2	6	4	2	0	18
Severe	0	0	0	2	6	4	0	2	14
Total	8	12	28	52	36	36	22	6	200
$\chi^2 = 66.12, df=21, P<0.05$									

Source: Authors Calculation

Table- 4 showed that children in the severe stunted category had poorer cognitive development, indicating that poor nutritional status had an impact on cognitive development. Stunted respondents performed well in the six below average group. Brain growth or mental capacity impairment was caused by the respondents' dietary state.

Table -5 Distribution of Pre-School children according to their weight and cognitive development

Cognitive Development status	Very Superior	Superior	High Average	Average	Below Average	Borderline defective	Mild	Moderate	Total
Normal	2	4	14	8	0	6	0	0	34
Mild	0	6	4	16	4	4	2	0	36
Moderate	4	4	6	10	14	14	4	2	58
Severe	2	0	4	18	18	12	16	2	72

Total	8	14	28	52	36	36	22	4	200
$\chi^2 = 71.62, df=21, P<0.05$									

Source: Authors Calculation

Table-5 indicated that cognitive development was affected by weight for height when dependency was analyzed. As the findings indicates that $p<0.05$, weight for height was an important component to consider when examining cognitive development. There were 18 wasted respondents in the average category, 18 below average, 16 in the moderate category, and 12 in the area of borderline defective respondents.

CONCLUSION

The present study was conducted to determine the association between the impacts of nutritional status on cognitive development pre-school children. According to the study, 6 percent of the respondents were severely stunted and 77% of the respondents were normal for their age and height. Similarly, 17% of the respondents were found to be normal for their weight for their height and 36% to be severely wasted. The study found that among the individuals selected pre-school children, the stunted rate is lower than the wasted rate. A statistical investigation revealed a significant ($p<0.05$) relationship between cognitive growth and milk and green leafy vegetables. The study also discovered that a non-vegetarian diet influences mental capacity development more than a vegetarian one does. The significance of the weight for height finding suggests that weight was an important factor to take into account while analyzing cognitive growth. There were 18 healthy respondents in the average group, 18 in the below-average group, 16 in the moderate group, and 12 in the borderline deficiency group. A high rate of waste is the main cause of inadequate cognitive growth. India is a developing nation where stunted and wasted children are common due to a high rate of malnutrition.

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